

EXPERIMENTAL POSTBUCKLING STUDY OF PRE-CONFORMED COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

An ideal thin plate under compression starts to buckle at a certain critical level of the load with the buckling pattern presenting the classical undulations or waves. Nevertheless, unlike bars, in which buckling implies the catastrophic failure of the element, plates and sheets are able to bear loads above the first (or greater) buckling loads. Ratios of 2 or 3, or even more, between the collapse and critical loads are referred to in the literature, this capacity to save weight having attracted the interest of the industry.

To take advantage of this promising feature presents, however, serious difficulties due to the fact that the evolution of a particular panel is largely influenced by many factors, geometric imperfections being of particular relevance. Therefore, nominally identical panels can evolve in a very different way along the near-buckling and postbuckling regime.

The idea of the present study is to analyze the possibility of avoiding this variability in the postbuckling behaviour of the panels by magnifying the influence of intentionally included imperfections. To this end, some panels were manufactured and tested under simply supported boundary conditions. A video correlation system (Aramis®) was used to follow the evolution of the panels, results being compared with Finite Element predictions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Usually, unlike bars, plates and sheets do not completely lose the bearing capacity when achieving the first buckling load, [1-4]. So, this load does not necessarily imply the collapse of the structure. This fact is particularly interesting in the case of stiffened panels, where the collapse of the component is defined by the occurrence of instabilities associated with the buckling of the stiffeners and/or the occurrence of debondings or delaminations [5,6]. In these cases, the local buckling of the skin between two stringers and two frames (in the case of an aircraft fuselage) has relatively little effect on the bearing capacity of the entire panel. Nevertheless, it can cause the appearance of detached zones between the skin and the stiffeners [7]. It is understandable that the prediction of these damages is critical to ensure safety of the structure in the postbuckling regime, i.e. after the first buckling load.

The main difficulty that designers and researchers have when predicting the behaviour in the postbuckling range of a particular panel is that this evolution is extremely sensitive to many factors, the most remarkable being the imperfections of the actual geometry of the panel and the support and load conditions [8,9].

Predicting the behaviour becomes a problem for each individual panel. In most cases the FEM is used with initial geometric imperfections being introduced by a combination of buckling modes. The coefficients in this combination are obtained by adjusting the function to the measures of a points cloud [9]. It is obvious that this procedure may be valid for one particular panel, but impracticable for

a batch, theoretically equals one to each other but actually different; which makes the use of such this procedure questionable in the design phase.

Focusing only on the aspects related to the initial geometry, it seems reasonable that very high modes (those whose corresponding buckling load is much higher than those under which the structure is going to work) are unnecessary, and that if any of the coefficients derived from the above adjusting process is far superior to the rest, its influence on the results should be higher as well. Based on this idea, this paper presents the first results of the analysis of pre-formed composite plates subjected to compressive load at the postbuckling regime. A similar idea, but with the aim of increasing the bearing capacity of cylindrical sheets, has been recently published [10].

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE SPECIMENS

2.1 Material

Squared plates were manufactured for the research, dimensions being 200×200 mm². The material used was unidirectional AS4/8552 plies, whose mechanical properties are shown in Table 1.

Engineering constant	Value	
E_1	128.061	GPa
E_2	9.79	GPa
ν_{12}	0.335	
G_{12}	5.722	GPa

Table 1: Mechanical properties for the AS4/8552.

The three stacking sequences shown in Table 2 were considered, 0° being the direction of the load. Each ply had a thickness of 0.13 mm.

Denomination	Stacking sequence	Thickness
S1	$[0_{12}]$	1.56 mm
S2	$[90_{12}]$	1.56 mm
S3	$[45_s, -45, 0, 45, -45, 90]_s$	1.56 mm

Table 2: Laminates stacking sequences (sub index 's' means symmetry).

2.2 Experimental setup

Although initially the boundary conditions described in [1,2,4] were considered because of the power of disposing an analytical solution for the postbuckling evolution, they were discarded due to the fact that it is really difficult to reproduce them in a laboratory. However, simply supported edges are relatively easy to reproduce. Thus, these boundary conditions were considered and Figure 1 shows a picture of the experimental setup with one of the specimens ready to be tested.

The plate was supported between four guides, each with a V-channel. The upper guide was movable but the other three were fixed. An auxiliary system was used at the upper side in order to prevent undesirable relative movement between the vertical guides.

The borders of the plates were manually prepared to be inserted in the V-channels of the guides in a way that allowed the rotation around the border of the plate but translation perpendicular to the border was prevented (except for the upper guide). If xy is the plane of the plate, the origin being at the centre of the plate, the setup tried to reproduce the following support conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_x(X/2,y) = 0 & & u_z(X/2,y) = 0 & & u_y(x,-Y/2) = 0 & & u_z(x,-Y/2) = 0 \\
 u_x(-X/2,y) = 0 & & u_z(-X/2,y) = 0 & & u_y(x,Y/2) = -\delta & & u_z(x,Y/2) = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

X being the length of the plate along x -direction and Y the length along the y -direction.

A universal testing machine was used. The device had to be carefully centered in the machine, so that the load was applied as uniformly as possible. The load cell of the machine was used to record the load applied, and the Aramis® optical system was used to record the full displacement field during the tests. This is the reason why the specimen shows a white dotted surface in the picture of Figure 1.

Figure 1: Experimental setup.

2.3 Preliminary analysis

In order to select the geometry for the pre-conformed plates, a numerical buckling analysis was previously done using Abaqus® software. The finite element model used was a shell model with 40×40 S8R elements. This is a conventional shell element with reduced integration [11]. Figure 2 shows the buckling results (deformed shape, red and blue representing opposite transversal displacements; load, F ; and shortening, ΔL) for the three laminates considered, the load being applied along y -direction (vertical in Figure 2).

Loads shown in Figure 2 correspond to bifurcation loads of the structure. At these points the theoretical evolution of the plate may remain plane or it may follow one of the postbuckling paths. Postbuckling paths can be obtained analytically for some specific support and load conditions (e.g. [1,2]), or in general cases using numerical tools, especially FEM [4]. To obtain the postbuckling branch with FEM, a perturbation of the geometry reproducing the corresponding buckling mode shape is introduced into the model [4], the amplitude of the perturbation being about 10% of the plate's thickness. To check if this situation can be reproduced experimentally, a pre-form reproducing one of the shapes shown in Figure 2 was selected.

The selected pre-form had 3 half-waves along one direction (horizontal or vertical) and 1 half-wave along the perpendicular direction (vertical or horizontal). Notice that these geometries correspond to modes 6 and 7 for the S1 laminate; 2 and 70 for the S2; and roughly 4 and 6 for the S3. With these geometries a wide range of ratios between the corresponding buckling loads and the critical loads (those corresponding to mode 1) are obtained, varying between 1.35 and 13.21.

Figure 2: Buckling modes for the ideal plate.

2.4 Perturbed geometry

Reviewing the buckling shapes shown in Figure 2, a perturbed geometry in the form (1) was considered, as most of the buckling modes are covered by the following expression:

$$z = Z \operatorname{sen} \left(n \pi \left(\frac{x}{X} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right) \operatorname{sen} \left(m \pi \left(\frac{y}{Y} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

Z being the amplitude of the perturbation, and m and n two natural numbers defining the number of half-waves along the load direction and along the perpendicular direction to the load, respectively.

To manufacture the plates with the pre-form (1), a mould was machined using a milling machine CNC TEC-CAM 3000. This mould was designed with one semi-wave along one direction and three half-waves along the other direction, Z in (1) being 2 mm.

Considering the two orientations of the mould with respect to the load direction, two pairs of (m,n) numbers are obtained: (1,3) and (3,1). Combining the three laminates (Table 2) with these two orientations of the mould, the six configurations shown in Figure 3 were manufactured. The first two characters refer to the laminate (S1, S2 or S3), and the last three to the number of half-waves along the load direction and perpendicular to the load direction, respectively (W13 or W31).

Table 3 summarizes the similarity between the pre-form and the buckling modes in Figure 2; F_b/F_{cr} being the ratio between the corresponding buckling load, F_b , and the critical load (the smallest buckling load), F_{cr} .

Figure 3: Configurations of the pre-conformed plates.

Configuration	Buckling mode	F_b / F_{cr}
S1W13	6 of S1	5.69
S1W31	7 of S1	7.25
S2W13	70 of S2	13.21
S2W31	2 of S2	1.35
S3W13	\approx 6 of S3	5.19
S3W31	\approx 4 of S3	3.48

Table 3: Similarity between pre-conformed geometries and buckling shapes for the ideal plate.

It can be said that the two configurations S2W31 and S3W31 (especially the first one) have small F_b/F_{cr} ratios; S1W13 and S3W13 have medium ratios; and the other two, S1W31 and S2W13 (especially the last one), large ratios.

Notice that, although perturbations shown in Figure 3 are intentionally introduced, the manufacturing process also introduces other inevitable imperfections, which are neither planned nor predictable.

3 BUCKLING ANALYSIS OF THE PRE-CONFORMED PLATES

Due to the perturbation of the geometry, buckling loads of the pre-conformed plates differ from those of the ideal plane plate. Figure 4 shows the critical buckling loads and shapes for the specimens assuming that the actual geometries follow expression (1).

Figure 4: Buckling modes for the pre-conformed specimens.

The critical mode for all the specimens is described by a unique dent, except for S2W31 which has apparently two dents along the load direction (really, it has another half-wave near the upper and lower bounds, but their amplitudes are quite small).

Notice that the ratios between the first buckling load of the specimens, F_{cr}^* , versus those corresponding to the ideal plane plate, F_{cr} , which are both shown in Table 4, present serious alterations: $F_{cr}^*/F_{cr} \approx F_b/F_{cr}$ for configurations S1W13 and S3W31; $F_{cr}^*/F_{cr} < F_b/F_{cr}$ for configurations S1W31, S2W13 and S3W13; and $F_{cr}^*/F_{cr} > F_b/F_{cr}$ for configuration S2W31.

Configuration	Buckling mode	F_b/F_{cr}	F_{cr}^*/F_{cr}
S1W13	6 of S1	5.69	5.41
S1W31	7 of S1	7.25	2.91
S2W13	70 of S2	13.21	2.31
S2W31	2 of S2	1.35	4.13
S3W13	\approx 6 of S3	5.19	3.14
S3W31	\approx 4 of S3	3.48	3.79

Table 4: Buckling loads for the pre-conformed specimens.

4 POSTBUCKLING ANALYSIS FOR THE PRE-CONFORMED PLATES

Tests were performed by increasing the load slowly and monotonically till a noise was noticed. Aramis® system pictures were recorded during the tests. As an example, Figures 7 and 8 compare the displacement perpendicular to the plate plane fields, u_z , measured by the Aramis® system with those obtained with Abaqus® for specimens S1W13 and S2W31 at loads equal to two and four times the critical load of the corresponding ideal plane plate. The Aramis® photographs have been superimposed on a picture of the specimen. Due to the characteristics of the device, some shadow areas appeared in the Aramis® photographs. The same scale is used for pictures along the same row, but scales differ from one row (Aramis®) to another (Abaqus®), except for the S2W31 specimen.

Figure 7: Experimental and numerical u_z field for the S1W13 specimen.

Figure 8: Experimental and numerical u_z field for the S2W31 specimen.

The agreement between predictions and experiments is very satisfactory on the one hand for configuration S2W31. However, on the other hand, the experimental evolutions differ substantially from the predicted numerical ones for S1W13 configuration. Specifically, the experimental evolutions show just one dent whereas the numerical one shows the development of three dents.

A prospective explanation of these discrepancies can be found by analysing the load-shortening evolution of each ideal specimen, i.e. without other imperfections like those intentionally introduced by the perturbation of the geometry, in conjunction with the ratios indicated in Table 4. These curves are shown by the designation FEMa in Figures 9 to 11. In these graphs, cross marks indicate the buckling load-shortening points for the ideal plane plate (in red) and the ideal perturbed specimen (in blue), and light blue rhombus' indicate experimental measures (measures for the S1W31 specimen were discarded because of problems when introducing the load).

Referring to the experimental data, the shortening was estimated from the Aramis® pictures in the following way:

1. A reference length was identified from the initial picture, because due to the presence of shadow areas, this reference length could not be the total length of the plate (200 mm).
2. The variations of this length were recorded from one picture to another.
3. The total shortening of the plate was computed as the average strain times the nominal length (200 mm).

The load was read from the load cell of the machine. It was not possible to have an automatic correlation between the applied load and the Aramis® picture, the load corresponding to each Aramis® picture being then recorded manually.

Let us focus on one particular case, for example: S2W13. The ideal S2W13 reproduces the buckling mode 70 of the ideal plane plate, buckling load being $F_b = 13.21 F_{cr}$. Thus, it was expected that the evolution would follow approximately the first order solution from zero till load level, F_b , and after that the panel would follow the postbuckling evolution for the 70th buckling mode. This is exactly what the numerical solution FEMa represents (a quasi-straight line crossing all the buckling points of the ideal specimen).

Figure 9: Load – Shortening evolution for the S1W13 and S1W31 specimens

Figure 10: Load – Shortening evolution for the S2W13 and S2W31 specimens

Figure 11: Load – Shortening evolution for the S3W13 and S3W31 specimens

Nevertheless, experimental measures are very different. To explain this, let us focus on the results of the buckling analyses of the ideal plane plate and of the ideal S2W13 specimen. The critical

buckling load for the ideal S2W13 specimen is $F_{cr}^* = 2.31 F_{cr}$, which is much smaller than the buckling load corresponding to the 70th mode of the ideal plane plate, $F_b = 13.21 F_{cr}$. Thus, the postbuckling evolution of the actual specimen will be sensitive to the imperfections of the geometry from near to $F_{cr}^* = 2.31 F_{cr}$ in advance. However, during the manufacturing process of the specimen it is inevitable that extra uncontrolled imperfections are introduced, the ideal evolution for the corresponding mode being really difficult to follow.

To clarify this fact, additional imperfections were considered in Figures 9 to 11. For simplicity, these imperfections were also modelled following the shape in (1). Two cases were analysed:

- $m = n = 1$ (which is roughly the first buckling mode for the ideal S1W13, S1W31, S2W13, S3W13 and S3W31 specimens) for FEMc ($Z = 0.2$ mm) and FEMe ($Z = -0.2$ mm) cases; and
- $m = 2$ and $n = 1$ (which is roughly the first buckling mode for the ideal S2W31 specimen) for FEMg ($Z = 0.2$ mm) and FEMh ($Z = -0.2$ mm) cases.

These predictions show very clearly that the new imperfections affect the evolutions starting from a load close to the first buckling load. The same reasoning can be applied to specimens S1W13 and S3W13.

Focusing now on the S2W31 specimen, the perturbation corresponds to the 2nd buckling mode of the ideal plane plate, the buckling load being only: $F_b = 1.35 F_{cr}$. Additionally, the critical load for the ideal specimen is: $F_{cr}^* = 4.13 F_{cr}$ being much higher than F_b . Additional imperfections would start to affect the results over the critical load, F_{cr}^* ; thus, the actual evolution of the test is predictive in the range of load till F_{cr}^* . Notice that corresponding FEMc, FEMe, FEMg and FEMh curves do not differ from original FEMa curves. The same reasoning can be applied to the S3W31 specimen, although in this case the difference between F_b and F_{cr}^* is smaller.

9 CONCLUSIONS

A set of pre-conformed plates were analysed experimentally and numerically. The main objective of this research is to understand the conditions for the predictability of the postbuckling evolution under the compressive load of a pre-conformed composite plate.

Simply supported conditions were considered, a specific device being designed and manufactured. Three stacking sequences of unidirectional composite laminates were tested. The pre-forms of the specimens were selected after the buckling analysis of the ideal plane plates; they were obtained using a mould. Combining the two orientations for the mould and the three stacking sequences, six specimens were manufactured. The mode reproduced by the pre-form for each stacking sequence and orientations varies from small (1.35) ratios between the corresponding buckling load and the critical one, to very large ratios (13.21).

The buckling analysis of the ideal specimen shows an increasing of the buckling load with respect to the ideal plane plate. These increments vary from 2.31 to 5.41 from one configuration to another.

Predictions were made numerically using Abaqus® finite element software. Agreement with experimental data is quite satisfactory for some cases, but not for others. Explanation of this discrepancy has to be found in the fact that inevitable imperfections were introduced during the manufacturing process, and they affect the evolution of the specimen throughout the test.

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